

Relativistic escape speed in the electric field

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We view n bodies with the positive charges $Q_1, Q_2, \dots, Q_n$ in a coordinate system in vacuum. $\vec{p}_1, \vec{p}_2, \dots, \vec{p}_n$ are the positions of the charges in R^3 .

Now we view a negative test charge Q on the position $\vec{p} \in R^3$. The problem is to move this charge to another position $\vec{r} \in R^3$. The necessary energy is:

$$\Delta W = \frac{Q}{4\pi\epsilon} \cdot \left| \sum_{i=1}^n Q_i \cdot \left(\frac{1}{|\vec{p} - \vec{p}_i|} - \frac{1}{|\vec{r} - \vec{p}_i|} \right) \right| \quad (1)$$

ϵ is the electric field constant and $|\cdot|$ the absolute value of vectors in R^3 . If the absolute value of $\vec{r}$ is infinite, we get the work that is necessary to move the test piece in the infinity.

$$\Delta W = \frac{Q}{4\pi\epsilon} \cdot \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{Q_i}{|\vec{p} - \vec{p}_i|} \quad (2)$$

If we want to calculate the necessary velocity, we must use the relativistic kinetic energy:

$$\Delta W = mc^2 \cdot \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}}} - 1 \right)$$

c is the light velocity, and m is the mass of the test piece. Now we transform this formula to the velocity v using equation (2) in Schröer [1]:

$$v = c \cdot \sqrt{1 - \left(\frac{mc^2}{\Delta W + mc^2} \right)^2} \quad (3)$$

We get the velocity that is necessary to move the test piece from $\vec{p}$ to $\vec{r}$ from equation(3), if we insert the equation (1) for ΔW . The escape speed consists of equation (3) by inserting the equation (2) for ΔW .

The charges positions $\vec{p}_1, \dots, \vec{p}_n, \vec{p}$ can be temporal functions. If we view the situation exactly, we have a time dilatation because of the charge movement. We don't consider this here. The time dilatation can be neglected, if all velocities are smaller than $\frac{c}{10}$.

References

- [1] Harald Schröer "Velocity and Temperature" 2009
- [2] Harald Schröer "Particular problems of special relativity theory" Wissenschaft & Technik Verlag Berlin 2002